

LESSON OBSERVATION

Thirty Lessons at Vaasa Övningsskolan: A Didactic Report on Inclusive Teaching, Learning Engagement, and Scaffolding Practices

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On the day of Seminar 2 (20/1/2025), our instructors, Linda Noorgran and Anna-Brita Slotte, asked us to picture an outstanding lesson: What do we see? What is going on in the lesson, and what is the teacher doing? By that time, I was already midway into my observation schedule, but these questions reshaped my vision of what I had observed and what was yet to come. I will attempt to answer this question towards the end of this report.

At Vaasa Övningsskolan, I not only observed a sequence of 30 lessons, but I also took a bird's-eye view of how English was taught in different classrooms, how teachers helped students understand the language, how they kept students interested, and how they made learning accessible for all. My observation included classes from elementary school to upper secondary (including the International Baccalaureate (IB)). The major aim of my observation was to analyse how teachers created inclusive classrooms, used scaffolded teaching, and encouraged interaction. This report reflects on these aspects, as well as how teachers build trust, use the latest technology, and adapt their teaching to meet student needs.

In this report, I also examine features of Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) and multilingual teaching. In the majority of the classes that I observed, teachers used English to explore topics in a variety of subjects, such as Science and History, thereby allowing students to practice the language in a real and issue-based context. Since many students speak both Swedish and English, the teachers smoothly switched between the two languages to enhance students' understanding. CLIL supports learning subject content more efficiently and multilingual classrooms foster language development and confidence, as teachers can easily switch between languages to aid comprehension (Denardi, 2017; Palacios Rojas & Juan Sebastián, 2018).

To emphasise the above, the teachers, especially at the upper secondary level, relied heavily on themes from the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 2030) in teaching English through a multidisciplinary lens. The students were exposed to topics such as circular economy (Economics), climate change (Geography), space (Physics), and imperialism (History), as well as one that I found particularly intriguing: zodiac star signs (Astronomy). In one of the lessons based on the SDGs, Johanna Soderholm (ENA07.2, 8/1/2025) tasked the students with choosing from the 17 goals and creating a project on possible solutions.

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This kind of learning activity supports inclusivity and engagement, making students feel like they are part of a real issue (Lempinen, 2017). In this lesson (ENA07.2, 8/1/2025), I observed that there was an effort to make learning as democratic as possible. Johanna allowed students to have their say in what kind of project they wanted to pursue and also the medium to execute it. Some students addressed poverty, while others worked on gender equality. While quite a number of them chose to write essays, a few created slides, and one opted to record a podcast. Saloviita (2018) highlights that students are more motivated and take ownership of their learning if they have a voice in the classroom.

At the heart of my business at Ovningskolan was to find out how scaffolding practices were evident in the day-to-day interaction between teachers and learners. The central idea was that almost all the teachers designed their lessons to strictly follow a path: simple to complex. In this path, for example, a new word or a set of words was introduced. Then the teacher provided examples of sentences where the words were used, and it became the students' turn to write their own sentences using the words. This simple scaffolding technique is fully realised in different forms and with various application measures, each time helping students feel more confident and aiding better comprehension (Hakamäki, 2005). In scaffolding, the teachers are never alone; they are assisted by interactive learning technology. The students played vocabulary games on the tablets and worked on group projects using digital tools (Itslearning, Fle3). Technology, ever-present in the classrooms, increases students' engagement and makes learning more dynamic (Alasalmi et al., 2015).

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My report will also examine the matter of personnel and teaching as a trust-based profession in Finland. I admired the figures cut by the teachers standing before the class as good models with the potential to inspire students. I saw this in the way they conducted their routines with effortless confidence and a remarkable awareness of time. They set rules for the class, and while they were firm about expectations, they still maintained a friendly atmosphere where students and their needs were respected. In that sense, there was trust between the system, the learners, and the teachers, which is important for a good learning environment (Kaznachevskaya, 2013). I also cherished the moments when I heard from teachers as they shared personal details about the changing times, particularly regarding educational policies and the curriculum, and how they navigate the highly demanding processes. One of the most significant changes is the move from the old one-way lecture style to a student-centred pedagogy, which encourages active participation and fosters better retention and understanding through interactive learning rather than passive listening (Fernandes et al., 2019).

What does an inclusive classroom look like?

An inclusive classroom is one in which every student feels welcome, is supported, and has the opportunity to participate in learning. It consists of structured interactions, physical space, and accommodations for different learning needs (Morcom & MacCallum, 2012). For me, defining an inclusive classroom is much easier than bringing it to fruition. During my observation, it was not easy to fully comprehend inclusion within a 45-minute lesson, as inclusion extends beyond the four walls of the classroom and can be interpreted through subtle and complex layers of meaning. While reflecting on this, one important question guided my observation: Do the teachers at Ovningskolan create a safe space where students feel comfortable enough to express themselves without fear of embarrassment or punishment?

Inclusion also encompasses the physical and organisational structure of the classroom. For example, how students are seated influences classroom interaction. On the first day of my observation, in Pia Valkeakari's class (English, Grade 5, 8/1/25), I noticed that boys and girls were seated separately. This somewhat dictated how students related to each other, particularly in group discussions. Boys mostly talked to boys; girls mostly talked to girls. According to Florian (2008), inclusion is not just about placing students in the same room; it's about ensuring that they can interact in a meaningful way. In this case, the students chose to sit according to their gender, and even though it didn't bother the teacher, it did attract my

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wandering eyes. I wondered how that arrangement might have inadvertently reduced opportunities for more inclusivity.

I also make a strong case for emotional inclusivity in the classroom. This lies in how the teacher encourages inclusivity by supporting students who require different ways of participating in class as feeling beings. I observed an interesting and funny episode in Sebastien Pelkikanga's class (English, Grade 4, 14/1/25). The students were assigned to create a presentation titled *About Myself* using their tablets and working with Canva. A few minutes earlier, they had danced merrily before the big screen, but it seemed that this particular task had wiped away all that joy. One student, who could no longer bear it, went to the back of the class and fell asleep. The interesting part was that the teacher let him be. To me, that was a show of respect for student autonomy and an acknowledgment that not all students learn in the same way. Inclusive teaching demands flexibility and an awareness that the emotional and cognitive needs of students are diverse (Penner, 2018).

Inclusivity also involves making sure every student has a role in any group activity. In an after-class chat with Diane–Christine Blusi (ENA05.3, 15/1/25), she shared with us the importance of having the teacher select and assign groups during activities like the think-pair-share we witnessed in her class. According to her, this ensures that no student is exposed to the possibility of being left out because they are not a member of a social clique (friends club), and it also provides an opportunity for students to work with peers they would not normally select. Sreckovic et al. (2018) affirm that the use of structured grouping strategies eliminates social exclusion and creates a sense of community in the classroom. However, as genuine as this approach is, it is still in the best interest of students when the teacher allows them to find and negotiate groups by themselves, as this naturally boosts their social skills (Kamens et al., 2003).

Most importantly, an inclusive classroom must cater to learners with different needs: second-language learners, reluctant learners, or neurodivergent students. Implementing this in the classroom does not always follow traditional patterns, such as providing visual aids for L2 learners; instead, it may simply involve slowing down speech so that students can process information at an appropriate pace. It may also require altering the lesson plan or adjusting established methods to better serve all students (Carrington, 2017; de Jong & Harper, 2011).

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For example, Jan Alin (English, Grade 4, 14/1/25) allowed some students to work in pairs rather than present before the whole class because they (as I later discovered) did not have enough English proficiency to confidently deliver their presentations. In another lesson, a student made an obvious mistake in his answer, and the teacher responded, "*Adam, that's an interesting way to think about it...*" This type of inclusion provides what Sayfulloevna (2023) describes as psychological safety—a classroom environment where students feel safe enough to take academic risks without the fear of being judged.

Scaffolding Learning and Providing Structured Support at Vaasa Övningsskolan

In the picture, Diane-Christine Blusi (ENA01 & ENA2.4, 15/1/25) took the students to the chapel. The task was simply for the students to pitch their ideas to one another based on the presentation they had created about a place they would love to travel to and why. The sheer brilliance in the teacher's choice of setting was evident in the spatial arrangement, with students alternating seats and rotating as if they were truly traversing the world—it was a class act in scaffolding!

Scaffolding is literally the process of helping students through different phases of a task, bit by bit, until they are able to stand on their own without being overwhelmed. It is a classroom strategy in which the teacher supports learners by providing structured assistance to help them tackle challenging tasks and improve their existing capabilities. Belland (2014) defines scaffolding as a dynamic process that makes tasks simpler by breaking them down into manageable parts while also providing a cushion for students to reach the main goals of a learning unit. In this process, the support gradually decreases as learners begin to master the task and eventually become capable of performing it without the teacher's intervention.

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I summarise scaffolding practices by teachers at Vaasa Övningsskolan into three core categories: structured support, differentiation, and responsive teaching. The structured support provided was gradually removed as the children developed confidence in their learning and became able to carry out tasks independently (Gibbons, 2002; Mahan, 2022). Differentiation is important to ensure that each student receives help at their unique operational level. In responsive teaching, teachers modify their instructions at intervals to meet the needs of students, thereby making learning more inclusive and productive (Pompetti-Szul, 1997). In the following paragraphs, I present key moments in the classroom that shaped my perspectives as they relate directly or indirectly to the core categories.

In the language didactics course with Marina Bendtsen, lesson discussions focused on embodied learning as a scaffolding technique and how teachers can utilise it in the language classroom. It was my first day of observation, and Pia Valkeakari (English, Grade 5, 8/1/25) engaged students in learning the parts of the body (vocabulary). She put her body to great use in the class, and I wondered if she had once trained to be an actor too (laughs). Then, she asked the students to do the same with their partners, having them guess which body part was enacted, and it was quite visible that the students enjoyed the session. The lesson concluded with an engaging game on Wordwall (an app that I have now shared with my colleagues in Nigeria, who are giving rave reviews), and the students practiced with the words they had learned in a fun and interactive way. In that lesson, movement was maximally utilised—and what students wouldn't appreciate a classroom walkabout? Macedonia (2019) observes that kinesthetic reinforcements in the classroom are especially good for L2 learners since physical movements help with improved vocabulary retention.

I observed how almost all the teachers scaffolded their lessons through a translation pedagogy that included translation exercises, bilingual comparisons, and code-switching. Jan Alin (English, Grade 6, 15/1/25) asked the students to match English and Swedish words, with the purpose of consolidating their bilingual understanding—distinguishing what is and what is not.

School – *Skola*

Student – *Elev*

Lesson – *Lektion*

Exam – *Prov*

Grade – *Betyg*

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Pedagogical translation strategies facilitate L2 learning through interconnections among languages (Nagy, 2015). However, in some cases, I felt that teachers were easily drawn into using Swedish because it was more reassuring for the students and saved time. Although translation may accelerate vocabulary acquisition, overusing it can undermine context-based immersive learning opportunities for children (Malik et al., 2023).

In Jennica Haga's class (English, Grade 8, 13/1/25), providing a model for the students was deftly used as a scaffolding technique. She asked the students to prepare for a class debate on the pros and cons of school uniforms, but first, they had to learn the type of debate and what was expected of them by watching a video demo of two teachers debating the same topic. This gave them a very clear idea of how to structure arguments and counterarguments. In modeling, as is typical in a classroom, learners observe an exemplary, well-structured example before they are expected to attempt the task (Matiso, 2024). The model in Jennica's class gradually shifted the students' focus from observation (appreciating the video) to independent thinking (formulating their own arguments).

Again, scaffolding can also be applied as a corrective measure, especially in situations where the teacher is dealing with contrastive linguistic items. A great example was Pia Valkeakari's (English, Grade 5, 14/1/25) attempt to differentiate between *I have a cold* and *I am cold* using examples in Swedish. It is common for ESL students to fall into interference errors. The teacher explicitly addressed this error through contrastive linguistic scaffolding—that is, she drew the students' attention to the differences in sentence structure between English and Swedish and how they differ or intersect. Contrastive scaffolding allows learners to recognize the complex nature of a target language by placing it side by side with their mother tongue (Korošec, 2012). This was very instrumental in avoiding major errors and improving linguistic accuracy.

Of all the scaffolding techniques listed, none was as common and constant as the use of assistive and digital technology. After one of the sessions, I had a long chat with my colleague Nelson Daramola, in which I expressed my fascination with the *document cameras* provided in the classes. Coming from the same country and having been English teachers for years in the same system, we poured out our hearts about how much difference it would have made to have such a piece of technology in our classrooms. My fascination took a new turn in Diane–Christine's class (ENA05.3, 9/1/25) when she collected data in real time using the Mentimeter app. She had just introduced a material for the students to work with and wanted

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to find out how well the students understood its content. So, the students charted their confidence levels on something that resembled a Likert scale.

In this scaffolding technique, the Mentimeter app became a diagnostic tool through which the students self-assessed their confidence and understanding. For the teacher, it served as a reliable means of gauging and providing real-time support for the students (Bukhari et al., 2023). In my reflection on the use of technology in classrooms, I asked a pertinent question: Is technology-supported scaffolding replacing structured teaching methods? While we have evolved to the point where technology is irreplaceable in the classroom, I sincerely hope that we do not cross the line where we lose sight of the value of teacher-led instruction (Bukhari et al., 2023).

The artwork below (unrelated) was something I found in the hallway at the upper secondary, and I could not help but marvel at the beauty of the lines. It appears to be an English translation of an Arabic poem (though I am not certain), and forgive me, but I would consider it selfish not to share.

*I have the desire to make you my bride,
to decorate the henna of my name on your hands,*

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to take away your misfortune, do the act of protecting you from evil eyes...

I have the desire, to make you mine.

(Author: unknown)

Learner Engagement: Teaching Strategies That Encourage Participation

I harbour this personal sentiment that most Finnish people speak in monotones. I may not be describing the authentic Finnish voice, but I have noticed how often I struggle with listening to even speech patterns—voices that are emotionally neutral. It is usually difficult for me to tell what the speaker is feeling, especially compared to the way the English language is spoken in my country—with expressive variation (I need to learn Finnish).

Then I met Diane—Christine Blusi (ENA05.3, 9/1/25). The tone and energy levels of the teacher affected how students reacted within the classroom. Diane's range of voice and the way she alternated between high, medium, and low tones—depending on the nature of the subject—was admirable. It was in her class that I wrote in my diary: *the students were truly awake!* It was because of this that I began to make a connection between learner engagement and a teacher's oratory skills. In her speech about the value of traveling, she said, *"No one remembers when they played video games at home, but they remember taking a picture with an elephant in Sri Lanka or being arrested in Morocco."* I laughed really hard. Bukhari et al. (2023) remark that humor and an engaging tone help create a friendly classroom environment that encourages student participation.

Another big factor in learner engagement is enabling and supporting students' choices about learning, which gives them a feeling of responsibility and involvement. Pia Valkeakari (English, Grade 6, 21/1/25) exemplified this with her method on Project UK. The students were tasked with exploring cultural patterns, events, and structures associated with life in England. For about 20 minutes, the students scoured the internet for things and places of interest. The key point was that Pia had instructed them to make their presentations about things they really liked or wanted, and it added to the overall excitement.

The final products were richly detailed. The students took us on a ride in the London Underground, we learned about the Top 5 Universities in the UK, and we *enjoyed* a British breakfast of bacon, sausages, and eggs. In all, the students were excited to share their findings

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because they had worked on something they had chosen themselves. I noticed something similar in the way Jan Alin (English, Grade 4, 14/1/25) worked hard to adjust the lighting in the room for better focus and engagement. Though this gesture might have appeared small, the change gave students a sense of control over their learning environment. Small adjustments in the classroom, like lighting, seating, and decor, can make students quite comfortable and participative (Potter, 2019).

Are schools making learning too fun?

This question came up in our discussion with Jennica Haga (English, Grade 7, 16/1/25) as she expressed concern about what would become of schools in the future with the current overemphasis on engagement over traditional academic rigor in the classroom. According to her, students are increasingly becoming addicted to fun, showing little interest in class activities that do not stimulate their senses in that regard. Therefore, is it a good idea to always allow students to choose what they learn? If granted, how would full ownership affect the realization of curricular goals? Opdecam and Everaert (2019) argue that although choice-based learning is effective and increases learner engagement, it should be balanced with structured instruction to deepen learning.

The same applies to the use of technology. It can significantly improve participation because lessons become interactive (Ramamuthie & Aziz, 2022; Topacio, 2018). It also encourages teamwork, helping students recall vocabulary (e.g., the use of the Quizlet app for word-matching: Jan Alin, Grade 6, 10/1/25). However, sometimes digital tools create distractions. In Jan Alin's class, for example, some students were more focused on the competition rather than the absorption of the material. Even though online platforms increase participation, teachers must guide their use so that learning does not lose its focal point (Mirzaev, 2022).

Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) and Multilingual Teaching

In the introduction, I mentioned that Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) occupies an important space in schoolwide pedagogical practices at Vaasa Ovningskolan. Lo and Lin (2019) define CLIL as a method of combining subject learning with language acquisition in order for learners to develop both content knowledge and language skills simultaneously. The Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) program

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in the upper secondary provided the grounds for CLIL practices to flourish. There was a funny situation when we thought we had joined the wrong class because the teacher was talking about space, latitude, longitude, and all that. In essence, almost all the subjects with topics related to the SDGs were discussed in the English language class. Johanna Soderholm (English, Grade 11, 10/1/25) integrated SDG 2030 themes into different projects for her students to join the conversation on global sustainability. It provided an immense opportunity for the students to develop their Cognitive Academic Language Proficiency (CALP) by acquiring new and advanced linguistic structures.

According to (Lorenzo and Rodríguez (2014), CLIL is especially convenient across subjects like the sciences that involve abstract reasoning and complex terminology. In this sense, students who are already proficient in their first language can easily find meaningful associations in the target language. It is, however, not usually a smooth process, especially for younger learners at the early stage of CALP development, as they have to deal with new academic content and the acquisition of advanced linguistic structures at the same time (Bentley, 2010; Gabryś-Barker & Bielska, 2013). Jennica Haga (English, Grade 7, 13/1/25) understood the assignment, and her style was simple. She made a long list of words and asked, *What is this called in Swedish?* Sometimes, the words lacked direct placements in Swedish, and they would look for the closest substitute or leave it as it was. To prevent the risk of overdependence on the first language, she allowed the students to switch between both languages in a planned manner (translanguaging): *In English, I want it only in English... okay, let's try Swedish now.*

Meanwhile, in Diane–Christine's class (ENA01 & ENA2.03, 15/1/25), some students had just returned from an exchange program in Bremen and Berlin (Erasmus+). It is noteworthy that in a CLIL program, students are not only learning a language for academic purposes; they also borrow insights from day-to-day or conversational language use (BICS)—and in this case, German. The students shared their authentic experiences with us, emphasising the difference between learning a language in the classroom and acquiring it through real-life interactions with native speakers. *(I felt this on a deeper level because I had just completed a four-month-long Swedish as a Second Language course in the classroom.)* This also underlines the importance of experiential learning as a key component of CLIL, because learners are more likely to acquire a language effortlessly when placed in authentic communicative situations (Cenoz et al., 2014; Evnitskaya, 2018).

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Democratic Learning

In a democratic-learning setting, students can negotiate their learning space. This particular lesson with Jan Alin (English, Grade 4, 14/1/25) took place in the auditorium. From what I learned, this was only possible because of an open discussion between him and the students about how the large space would benefit them. As a result, the students worked hard to ensure that it was a successful outing—running to print extra materials and eagerly answering questions. The impact was tangible. They spoke more freely and clearly appreciated the change of environment, most likely because the auditorium was less confining than a typical classroom. Democratic classrooms draw students into decision-making, enabling them to take ownership of their education through participation (McLeod, 2005; Pereira, 1993).

In Seminar 1 with Principal Mats Borgmstars, he mentioned that democratic learning is a hot topic in Teacher Continuous Professional Development Programs (CPD). He referred to seminars like those organised by e-Norssi, where teachers from across cities and municipalities gather to share and shape ideas through collaboration. Mats expressed that opinions are usually divided. The teachers shared their practical experiences and concerns. Some felt that giving students too much control could lead to a loss of structure, while others argued that guided participation creates a balance. Well, one shoe size does not fit all. Téllez (2016) highlights that the most important thing about democratic learning is recognising that students are active agents in the classroom rather than passive recipients. On the other hand, Auerbach (2005) restates that democratic learning must be structured so that students' input is not without the teacher's direction, to avoid counterproductive outcomes.

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After nearly a week of observing lessons, my team and I felt that something was still shrouded in mystery: teachers grading students' work. We had witnessed numerous tasks and assignments being completed in class, yet we had not seen teachers handing out already graded papers. This was inconsistent with our worldview as English teachers, who were accustomed to the schematic grading of students' work. My team appointed me as their spokesperson, and I took our curiosity to Jennica Haga's desk (English, Grade 8, 20/1/25). She took her time to explain that she provided feedback to her students but often without attaching numerical grades. She pointed out dropping comments-only feedback and, at times, just oral feedback.

This is another example of democratic learning through a trust-based assessment system. According to Johnson (2015), students who benefit from this approach develop a view of learning as a process rather than a competition. The democratic concept is based on a system that ensures fairness for all and prioritizes students' growth and development rather than merely ranking them against each other (Sinno, 2019).

Do Flexible Environments Always Improve Learning?

I curated the following quotes in my attempt to provide a meaningful response.

A structured opportunity for members of a class or school to meet and make decisions provides several advantages: it helps children feel respected by making it clear that their opinions matter; it builds a sense of belongingness and community; and it contributes to the development of social and cognitive skills such as perspective taking (imagining how the world looks to someone else), conflict resolution, and rational analysis. (Kohn, 1993, p. 7).

The essence of the demand for freedom is the need of conditions which will enable an individual to make his own special contribution to a group interest, and to partake of its activities in such ways that social guidance shall be a matter of his own mental attitude, and not a mere authoritative dictation of his acts

– John Dewey (Democracy and education).

Teacher Competence and Professionalism and the Finnish Concept of Trust

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In Finland we enjoy the freedom to be able to do our jobs without anyone looking over our shoulders.

Those were the words of Diane–Christine Blusi on the day of our final seminar (6/2/25). It was part of her response to my question about what it felt like to be a teacher in Finland (I was looking for personal truths). A lot of what happens in the Finnish education system is guided by trust, and this in itself is unique and admirable. There is trust in assessment, where teachers exercise the freedom to evaluate students in ways that reflect their real learning rather than just assigning grades. There is trust in the near absence of standardized testing, which reduces the fear of failing. There is also trust in the way Finnish teachers are placed in a position of high trust to make professional decisions without constant external control (Sahlberg & Walker, 2021). It is a privilege that is rare in my home country—where there are serious regulations and accountability measures for teachers, in a way that encroaches upon their sense of professional identity.

Lavonen et al. (2015) emphasise that Finnish teacher professionalism is built into the kind of education and training teachers receive. Teachers undergo challenging academic programs and are even required to commit to continuous learning on an ongoing basis. Therefore, trust is institutional. It is not just handed over to anyone but must be earned through professional development firmly in place. Harðarson (2022) further explains that trust and professionalism complement each other, as teachers who feel trusted are more likely to take responsibility for their work and strive for excellence.

We met Katrina Domar-Brannkarr (ENA01 & ENA2.4, 16/1/25), who was in her 39th year as a teacher, and she shared with us her journey and how she cracked the work-life balance code over the years. For someone who had spent many years doing the same thing, we were utterly impressed by her level of energy and how she interacted so fluidly with learners who were so many generations away from her. I was inspired.

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Final Thoughts

I saw many classrooms with mini-libraries like this one, filled with *mouthwatering* books, yet I could not find a student reading a novel in a corner. However, in quite many places, I noticed students pressing their phones, fully immersed in them and not noticing that someone had just passed. Within the corridors of Finnish schools, the widespread use of mobile phones is perceived to provide immense opportunities for innovation as well as a worrying source of concern bordering on misuse or abuse. On the positive side, mobile phones are considered one of the most accessible and efficient tools for learning, providing digital resources and interactive educational media (Vihavainen et al., 2010). On the other hand, however, the presence of mobile phones in schools poses a great concern to stakeholders due to their potential as tools for distraction in the classroom, cyberbullying, and the possible negative effects on the social fabric of students' lives and mental well-being (Li et al., 2012).

Diane–Christine Blusi (ENA05.3, 15/1/25) was one of the teachers who was quite clear about her no-phone policy in the classroom. That seemed like a good idea to keep students focused. However, I observed in some other classes that students used their tablets to engage in non-school-related activities. Even though phones were not allowed, some students found ways to use their tablets or laptops for distractions. Kay et al. (2017) discovered in a study that strict phone bans in schools may only make students sneakier about their use. Schools are adapting to this challenge by implementing short phone breaks or allowing phone use for very specific classroom tasks. At Vaasa Övningsskolan, students in both upper and lower secondary observe lunch breaks carefully squeezed in between hour-long classes. This is also usually an opportunity for them to check what's happening on TikTok or catch up with their friends on Instagram.

Furthermore, I observed how teachers at Vaasa Övningsskolan used time efficiently in the classroom—making it a culture to start and end lessons on time, ensuring that every

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minute contributed toward the lesson's objectives. I recommend that during observations, student-teachers should have access to the teacher's plan, as this would help them assimilate the technicalities behind planning and delivering a lesson. Most of the teachers structure their lessons to follow a noticeable pattern: a time for discussion, a time for practice, and a time for reflection. Good time management leads to better student outcomes, as it provides the right structure and ensures that all key points in a lesson are covered (Brown & Lee, 2015).

To conclude, I promised in the introduction that I would attempt to answer the question: What is an outstanding lesson? I received one of the greatest surprises in Inci Rotkirch's class (English, Grade 5, 8/1/25). She introduced her lesson on reading and modal/auxiliary verbs by playing a lyric video of the song *King of the World* by the Swedish band *First Aid Kit*. It was a pleasant surprise for me, and I think for the students as well. The song set the tone for the emotional response required for the next reading task. While the students engaged with the poetic lines in the song and tried to make sense of them, Inci incorporated their interest into the modules of her lesson. To me, an outstanding lesson is one in which the teacher is not afraid to take risks. To step slightly away from conventions, embrace new norms and aptitudes, and provide students with fresh opportunities and challenges in their environment—one they are not used to. Creativity in teaching makes students remember concepts better and enjoy learning (Sawyer, 2019).

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